

TECHNOLOGY OF MAKING DETAILS FROM POWDER MATERIALS

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Annotation. Nowadays, it is possible to obtain alloys from metals that are insoluble in each other, as well as hard-to-melt and ultra-pure metals when diluted by powder metallurgy methods. In powder metallurgy, sketches are made, as well as various details with precise dimensions. Powder metallurgy allows the preparation of porous materials and details, as well as details in the form of two (bimetals) or several layers of different metals and alloys. Powder metallurgy methods have high fire resistance and corrosion resistance. The process of obtaining details and products from powder materials consists of preparation of metal powder, forming of powder from them, pressing and baking. Metal powders are obtained by mechanical and physical-chemical methods.

Key words: detail, metal powder, pressing, dielectric, steel drum, granulometric.

In mechanical methods, powders are produced by crushing solid metals, and liquid metals without changing their chemical composition. Ball, impact and vibration mills are used to grind brittle hard materials. The material to be processed is crushed by impact or friction effect of steel or cast iron balls. It is necessary to take into account their pollution when extracting metal powders by mechanical methods. A ball mill consists of a steel drum [1].

The material placed in the chamber (a piece of wire, shavings, shavings and other small pieces) is carried away by the air flow, they collide with each other and are crushed into particles with a size of 50 to 200 μm . The resulting particles are plate-like, with serrated edges. Vibrating mills are used to obtain fine powders from brittle metal carbides and oxides. Vibrating mills are the most productive, their work is based on the frequency impact of steel balls and cylinders on the material to be crushed due to the high-frequency rotational vibration of the mill drum. To obtain tin, lead, aluminum, copper, as well as iron and steel powders, the method of refining liquid metal with the kinetic energy of air, water, steam or inert gases is also used [2].

The resulting powder particles have a size of 50-350 μm and are close to spherical in appearance. When making powders by physico-chemical methods, the chemical composition and properties of the starting material change. Chemical reduction of metals from oxides, electrolysis of diluted salts, carbonyl and hydrogenation methods are the main physicochemical methods. Chemical reduction of materials from oxides is carried out with gaseous or solid reducers. Natural, blast furnace gases, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen are widely used as gaseous regenerators. The porous metal mass formed as a result of chemical reduction is crushed. This method is the cheapest among the physico-chemical methods of obtaining powder. Powders of pure and rare metals (tantalum, zirconium, etc.) in the form of dendrites with a size of 1-100 μm are obtained by electrolysis of diluted metal salts. The electrolysis method makes it possible to obtain clean powders from contaminated raw materials. The carbonyl method allows obtaining spheroidal magnetic iron, nickel and cobalt powders with a size of 1-800 μm . The product obtained by this method decomposes into metal powder and carbon oxide at a temperature of 200-300°C. The hydrogenation method is based on the reduction of chromium with calcium hydrate. The resulting lime is washed with water, and the metal powder consists of 8-20 μm dendrites [3].

Dosed portions of powder with certain chemical and granulometric composition and technological properties are mixed in drums, mills and other devices. Alcohol, gasoline, glycerin, and distilled water are added if there is a problem with mixing the mixture evenly. Sometimes in the mixing process, technological additives are added that perform different tasks: plasticizers (paraffin, stearin, glycerin, etc.) to facilitate pressing, easily liquid additives to obtain products with the required porosity, volatile substances are added. Drafting and shaping of objects. Powders are pressed by cold or hot rolling and other methods. In cold pressing, concrete is placed in the press mold matrix and pressed with a working punch. After the pressure is obtained, the part is removed from the matrix with a pusher punch. During the pressing process, the powder particles are deformed elastically and plastically. In this case, the adhesion between the powder particles increases, and the porosity decreases. This allows you to get an outline of the desired shape and strength [4].

The outline is pressed in hydraulic or mechanical (eccentric, curved) presses. Pressing pressure is 200-1000 MPa depending on the powder composition and the function of the product. Automatic moving presses are common. The slag placed in the receiving hoppers moves to the filling hose by its

own weight. The hose ends on the press die 3, which can be pushed along the press table 4. The position of the bottom pusher punch 5 determines the amount of powder to be poured, that is, in this case, the dosage of the press die and its filling are performed simultaneously. When the press mold is full, the hose is moved aside and the powder can be compressed with a high working punch. The mold is pushed out with the lower punch, a hose is pushed to fill the mold again, and the mold is pushed down from the table to a special chute. Such presses are sometimes equipped with rotary tables on which several press dies are installed. The productivity of automatic pressing can be as high as producing several thousand sketches per hour.

In hot pressing, the product is not only formed in the press mold, but also baked, which allows to obtain a non-porous material with high physico-chemical properties. Hot pressing can be done in a vacuum, in a protective or return atmosphere, at a wide temperature range (1200-1800°C), at a much lower pressure than cold pressing. Usually, the powders are compressed under pressure after heating to the desired temperature. These methods are used in the preparation of products from hard-to-deform metals (borides, carbides, etc.). Rolling of metal powders is a continuous process of obtaining products in the form of strips, wires, strips by means of cold or hot deformation. Rolling is performed in vertical, oblique and horizontal directions.

Rolling in the vertical position is the best condition for forming the product. First, the powder falls from the hopper into the space between the rotary compacting rollers, is compressed to form a rough shape, then it is directed to the furnace for baking, and then it is rolled on clean rollers. During rolling, the size of the powder decreases several times. When rolling a strip, the ratio of the diameter of the roller to the thickness of the strip should be from 100:1 to 300:1. The speed of powder rolling is much lower than the speed of rolling cast metal and is limited by the fluidity of the powder. Therefore, the linear speed of the surface of the rotating rollers should be smaller than the speed of the metal powder moving out of the hopper and into the gap between the rollers. They are baked to give the necessary strength and hardness to the details and products.

They are baked to give the necessary strength and hardness to the details and products. The cooking operation consists of heating the product up to 0.6-0.8 of the temperature at which the main component liquefies and keeping it at this temperature for a certain time. Cooking is done in resistance electric ovens by induction heating or by passing current directly through the

item being cooked. To prevent metal powders from oxidizing, cooking is performed in argon, helium, vacuum or hydrogen environments. Thin and flat parts are baked under pressure so that they don't stick. In order to give the products a precise shape and precise dimensions, they are subjected to finishing operations; it is calibrated, cut, chemically thermally processed, brought to the required size by electrophysical methods, re-pressed. Calibration consists of pressing the pressed object through a suitable cut hole in the press die. As a result of calibration, the product's dimensions are determined, its surface is smoothed, and its porosity is reduced.

Obtaining complex-shaped details from pressed zagotovka (rollers for stretching, hard alloy gaskets, stamping matrices, etc.); internal and external carving; The diameter is small, but deep holes are cut into them. The presence of porosity, that is, the presence of a spread surface, makes it possible to carry out the process of chemical and thermal processing. Electrophysical methods with electric spark and electric pulse are used to obtain details of complex shape. The essence of the electric spark method is the use of a spark discharge with an electric pulse between two electrodes. In this case, the processed sketch acts as an anode, a tool, and a cathode. When working in the electric pulse method, reverse polarity is used to connect the electrodes. These methods depend on the erosion of the junction when pulsed electric current is passed through current-carrying electrodes. Due to the resulting discharge, the temperature on the surface of the rough electrode to be processed rises to 10,000-12,000°C in a very short period of time, and then the metal liquefies and vaporizes. The metal separated from the zagotovka solidifies in the form of particles in the medium of the dielectric liquid. Re-pressing method is used to obtain details of complex shape. As a result of re-pressing, the necessary dimensions and shape of the outline are provided.

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